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THE NEED TO USE DIFFERENT TYPES OF TASKS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES AT A NON-LINGUISTIC HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Abstract. This article deals with the topic of the necessity to use different types of tasks in foreign language classes at a non-linguistic university. In such a rapidly changing world, it is important to train a specialist in any professional field in accordance with the requirements of modern society and business environment. It is possible to form important professional and soft skills – ability to communicate, independence, ability to work in a team – in the foreign language classes in a higher education institution under the condition of using a variety of tasks, relying both on teaching aids and developing ones adapted to a particular group of students in accordance with the curriculum. Factors influencing the choice of tasks are highlighted: the level of language skills, the level of intelligence, learning motivation, creativity, adequate self-esteem of students. The main types of tasks according to the aspects of foreign language learning are distinguished: aimed at teaching receptive (reading, listening), productive (speaking, writing) types of speech activity, as well as those aimed at the formation of vocabulary and mastery of grammatical structures and phenomena. It is important to integrate all types of tasks into the foreign language learning process, clearly structuring them and adapting them to each group of students while implementing an individual approach. As a result of proper planning, lesson structure, selection and structuring of tasks in different formats, excellent results can be achieved not only in building communicative competence in students, but also in developing hard and soft skills and their creativity, which will help future professionals in their future careers.

Keywords: types of tasks, learning process, variability in usage, competence building, skills

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НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ ВИДОВ ЗАДАНИЙ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В НЕЯЗЫКОВОМ ВУЗЕ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается тема необходимости использования различных видов заданий на занятиях по иностранному языку в неязыковом вузе. В условиях столь быстро меняющегося мира важно подготовить специалиста любой профессиональной сферы в соответствии с требованиями современного общества и бизнес среды. На занятиях по иностранному языку в высшем учебном заведении возможно формировать важные профессиональные и гибкие навыки – способность к коммуникации, самостоятельность, возможность работы в команде при условии использования разнообразных заданий, опираясь как на учебные пособия, так и разрабатывая адаптированные варианты заданий к конкретной группе студентов в соответствии с учебной программой. Отмечаются факторы, влияющие на выбор заданий: уровень языковой подготовки, уровень интеллекта, учебная мотивация, креативность, адекватная самооценка учащихся. Выделяются основные виды заданий в соответствии с аспектами изучения иностранного языка: направленные на обучение рецептивным (чтение, аудирование), продуктивным (говорение, письмо) видам речевой деятельности, а также направленные на формирование лексического запаса и овладение грамматическими структурами и явлениями. Важно интегрировать в процесс обучения иностранному языку все виды заданий, четко структурируя их и адаптируя к каждой группе студентов, осуществляя при этом индивидуальный подход. В результате грамотного планирования, построения занятия, подбора и структурирования заданий в разных форматах можно добиться отличных результатов не только в формировании у студентов коммуникативной компетенции, но и развитии профессиональных и гибких навыков, творческого потенциала, что поможет будущим специалистам в дальнейшей профессиональной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: виды заданий, процесс обучения, вариативность использования, формирование компетенций, навыки

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Today's world is changing at an enormous speed. Accordingly, all areas of people's lives are changing, which undoubtedly has a significant impact on professional activities in any field. The ability to quickly and efficiently adapt, streamline, modify and optimize all current processes according to external conditions is almost basic, especially for young professionals, yesterday's graduates, just starting their career path in the new realities. In this regard, we can confidently state that one of the key tasks set for higher education institutions is to train professionals who are able to respond confidently, clearly and as appropriately as possible to all changes taking place, feel comfortable with themselves and function effectively in this environment.

Auditorium and self-study classes in any format in all subjects in higher education institutions, especially in core subjects, conducted in accordance with the programmes, are structured so as to fully meet all the current objectives. Foreign language classes provide an excellent opportunity to develop not only directly communicative competence in the language taught, which is undoubtedly the main goal, but also for self-development and self-expression of students, forming, training, embedding various soft skills, and other necessary skills, expanding the general outlook of students. [3]

On the example of foreign language classes in RSUTS, taught to students studying such specialties as tourism, hospitality, real estate service, geoinformation service, management, state municipal administration, graphic design, environment design, clothes design, law, etc., we will consider the necessity of using different types of tasks offered to students. Moreover, these tasks can perform not only their main function – to form communicative competence in a foreign language, but also serve as a means of development of flexible and professional skills, so essential for specialists in present-day conditions, as well as development of students' creativity. [2] According to I.A. Zimnya's definition, "student body includes people who purposefully, systematically master knowledge and professional skills, characterized by the highest educational level, the most active consumption of culture and a high level of cognitive motivation". [4]

It should be noted that the field of study of a future professional has a direct influence on the choice and preference for the use of one or another type of foreign language task, especially in the second, third and fourth year, when students have a foreign language in the professional sphere in their curriculum. However, only variety, flexibility, clear structure, careful planning as well as consideration of language competence degree are able to give the expected result.

In addition, students' individual psychological characteristics have a great impact on the final result, as follows:

- level of intelligence (ability to learn and remember, to understand and apply abstract concepts to solve problems);
- learning motivation, both extrinsic (for assessment or external validation) and intrinsic, implying interest in the subject and the process, (willingness to learn, involvement in the learning process, effort to achieve learning goals), causing strong positive emotions and feelings while achieving goals in the learning activity
- creativity (ability to create something new);
- adequate self-esteem.

The processes of learning and personal development are closely linked. According to L.S. Vygotsky, this dynamic relationship changes with age, and developmental processes do not coincide with learning processes. [1] He defined the "zone of the nearest development" and the tasks which at a certain stage of development the student is able to solve only with the help of the teacher, not independently. These tasks can be independently accomplished over time as the cognitive abilities develop. It is necessary to pay attention to this process when dealing with students.

When developing, structuring and implementing assignments, it is important to take all these factors into account along with the individual approach, especially taking into account the fact that multi level students are often taught in the same group at a non-linguistic university. Students with a lower level of language competence are in great need of help, psychological assistance, approval, positive assessment of even minor achievements, the smallest possible

intermediate results, particularly in the first year, at the very beginning of their studies during the period of adaptation. The effectiveness of educational processes depends on how quickly a student adapts to the surroundings of his or her new existence. [5, 6] Students with a higher language proficiency level should be offered additional tasks and projects to complete. Under certain conditions, we encourage students with different backgrounds to work together, because the stronger ones feel needed and involved in the process, while the weaker ones feel helped and supported. In this way, both parties gain experience in teamwork, which boosts motivation and prepares them directly for professional activities and further work in the company. In this way, an individually tailored approach is achieved in a group format.

All tasks in a foreign language, regardless of whether they are included in a textbook or are developed directly for some material by the teacher, can be divided into groups according to the type of speech activity: receptive types – reading, listening, and productive – speaking, writing; as well as tasks aimed at introducing, training and consolidating grammar structures and phenomena and tasks for introducing new lexical units and further work with them. However, this classification is very arbitrary, since all types of activity are closely intertwined and interrelated, and by activating one type, the others are automatically included in the process. Consequently, it is impossible to imagine the learning process without using and activating all activities at the same time.

For example, if we are talking about teaching reading, the main task is to activate this particular process, appropriately, when working with a text. In addition, when answering questions and completing other suggested text-based tasks, students either work orally or take notes, thus including productive activities such as speaking and writing. If we are talking about written tasks, students are asked to write any kind of work – a business or informal letter, a review, a story, an article, an essay, a summary with elements of their own opinion, etc. At the final stage, we offer discussions, debates, which is also participation in the speaking process. In addition, during the whole process of completing tasks, the

students listen to their own and their colleagues' answers and the teacher's instructions, thus including them in the process of listening – understanding information by ear. When dealing with a text on a particular topic, mainly professional ones, we pay attention to the vocabulary units, building up the students' vocabulary with the help of tasks to expand their vocabulary, and ensure grammatically correct speech construction, which trains the correct use of grammatical phenomena and structures in speech.

Conventionally, we can talk about the following tasks in the reading section:

Part 1. The aim is to gain a general understanding of the main idea of the text:

- skim (quickly read) the text;
- choose a heading (multiple choice);
- choose subheadings for each paragraph (each part) of the text;
- identify the main idea of the text.

Part 2. The aim is to gain a deeper understanding of the text, paying attention to detail:

- read the text;
- work with vocabulary (we suggest translating or giving definitions of the words in a foreign language, or relating foreign equivalents to Russian ones or to their definitions, depending on the students' level of proficiency;
- read the statements and say which ones are true and which are false; correct the false ones; find proofs in the text;
- answer the questions (or choose one correct answer to a question out of several suggested answers);
- fill in the blanks in the sentences;
- fill in the table;
- make a graph;
- match these words and phrases with synonymous expressions;
- using the dictionary, find antonyms for the words and phrases etc.

Part 3. The aim is to consolidate and discuss the information given in the text using active vocabulary and grammatical constructions:

- express your agreement/disagreement;

- summarise the content, adding elements of your own opinion at the end;

- in pairs (groups), discuss the advantages and disadvantages of the concept (depending on the content of the text)

- role-play the dialogues etc.

Part 4. The aim is to integrate into the learning process the topics and concepts that students have been introduced to in the classroom, develop project activities, intensify oral language practice in a foreign language in an extracurricular, informal setting:

- conduct a sociological survey and identify the degree (in %) of satisfaction and concern or dissatisfaction with everyday problems in the dormitory (for example, if the topic under consideration is "Student life", 1st year);

- make video clips on the topic;

As we can see from the examples of the above tasks, they are all aimed at teaching reading and, therefore, working with text. But of course, although the primary objective in this case is to teach reading, all kinds of speech activities are included in the process with no exception.

In the listening section, the following tasks are usually used:

- listen to an interview (dialogue, news extract, review, etc.) and note the topics that are raised in the extract (a list of suggested topics is provided);

- answer the questions;

- say which statements are true and which are not;

- identify what the numbers, data, etc. refer to;

- fill in the table;

- try to guess the meaning of words (terms) from the context etc.

In the work on the development of listening comprehension the same stages as in the work on reading comprehension can be noted: understanding the main idea, then detailed comprehension, scanning specific information (numbers, dates, names, etc.) and correlating them with relevant data, discussion of suggested questions (based on the main topic of the text), etc.

As we can see from the examples of tasks, their choice directly depends on the goal set by the

teacher working with a certain group of students – understanding of the main idea, deeper understanding, highlighting specific information, etc.

Despite the fact that we work at a non-linguistic university, we consider it appropriate to acquaint students with different dialects, peculiarities of pronunciation depending on the nationality of the speaker and even belonging to a particular social group. [8] These phonetic skills will significantly help future professionals to communicate more easily in a foreign language with customers from different countries, which is especially urgent for graduates in such specialties as "tourism" and "hospitality industry".

When teaching speaking, we have an excellent opportunity to design a variety of tasks. We use the tasks in the textbooks, modify them as necessary and develop our own, taking into account factors such as language proficiency, individual psychological characteristics, motivation, students' self-esteem and the general atmosphere in the group, as these tasks require students to communicate with each other in pairs or groups. When discussing, we can form pairs and small groups according to the factors mentioned above. Depending on the task at hand, groups are formed either by language level or mixed, so that the stronger students can provide guidance and the weaker ones can feel supported and helped at this stage.

In the speaking section we use the following tasks:

- answer the questions in pairs;

- discuss the topics;

- give reasons for your statements;

- act out a dialogue about a topic;

- round-table discussion;

- debate;

- express your own opinion etc.

When carrying out professionally and business-oriented assignments in senior year courses, specific business tasks can be proposed, options can be found and the best ones selected. For example, an assignment is given to select one of several candidates for a travel agent position (restaurant manager, hotel administrator, web-designer, depending on the area of training), information on the requirements for candidates and profiles of applicants is provided. Students first discuss in pairs or mini groups and then

meet in a single group to make the final decision on who in their view is the best candidate for the position and why. In this form of work we develop not only communicative competence but also soft skills which are so necessary in any profession – the ability to persuade, to assert one's point of view, the ability to listen, to make quick decisions, flexibility and others. It is especially when performing tasks aimed at developing speaking skills to eliminate the language barrier that a comfortable psychological environment in the class is very important, which the teacher supports during the whole process of work. E.N. Solovova notes that "benevolent relationships ... between all group members, awareness of the group as people who are close in spirit, some kind of community ready to help, forgive mistakes, listen to radical judgments, etc. will help overcome many difficulties". [7]

It is very important to formulate the instructions for the tasks accurately, sometimes it is necessary to do this in writing and to explain and clarify everything that needs to be done. For example, often in the initial stages, when the task is to discuss something in pairs, the students, after some time given for discussion, repeat what they have said during the preparation process in the form of a dialogue. The task should therefore be made clear: discuss what you think about a topic with each other, then, give your partner's opinion or your common judgement. Alternatively, ask students in pairs or groups to find solutions to situations, draw conclusions, etc. Be sure to specify the time allocated to a task, so that the students can manage how long they can do it. Gradually they become accustomed to a certain pace and the process becomes comfortable.

Teaching writing is very important nowadays, especially because of the prioritisation of modern means of communication such as social media, instant messaging, emails, etc. Starting to work with writing in the first year within general topics and tasks – a letter to a friend, a composition, an abstract, an essay – and progressing to more complex professional topics – a response to a customer complaint, a hotel or restaurant review, a memorandum, the minutes of a meeting, the result of negotiations – we follow the principle of gradual increasing in complexity. It is important to introduce students to a variety of stylistic techniques depending on the purpose of the written expression.

Teaching Grammar.

Such an absolutely integral part of foreign language teaching, as acquainting, mastering and practising grammar material, traditionally represented only the performance of grammatical exercises, clearly structured, arranged in a correct sequence according to the principle of gradual complication. In the final part of some module, representing a group of tasks for working through a grammatical phenomenon, students were offered the so-called reverse translation – from their native language into a foreign language, so long as they successfully completed it, we could judge that the grammatical material had been mastered and we should move on to the next section.

In today's world of information technology we have access to a vast amount of Internet resources such as programmes, mobile applications, online courses, videos and audio materials. With the help of these sources it is possible to make grammar learning more diverse, engaging and exciting for students, so that a apparently predictable part of learning grammar can become very engaging. For example, film clips, songs or excerpts can be used to consolidate the material. You can offer the option of using developed applications such as "English through stories"¹, "Learn English with TV series"², "English with movies"³, etc... "Learning English with movies", etc... Based on experience and practice, we can say that students, using foreign language songs as a resource on a regular basis, find themselves at a level where they are able to extract grammatical structures from song lyrics and identify them when listening to songs in their everyday life. It should be noted that the use of additional Internet resources can take place in the classroom as well as be offered as independent work and be recommendatory in character. Moreover, such interactive forms have positive emotional connotations and have a beneficial effect on the psychological environment of the group – students sing together or role-play situations from the song.

¹ <https://youtu.be/l-VCVHLuoi4>

² <https://youtu.be/csllyPzMLWg>

³ <https://youtu.be/pKoH9GkEKxQ>

In addition, after watching and analyzing a fragment of a film, the students also perform a short scene, which can be combined with role play – assigning a director, actors, or offering to take part in a TV show, etc. The use of works of art can also be included in grammar teaching – describing a painting in the present continuous tense, practising the construction "There is/are", etc. This is a serious stimulus to broaden the general outlook of the students and to introduce them to art and culture.

As experience shows, such forms of work, combined with traditional grammar exercises, not only improve the results, but are also a powerful motivational tool for learning a foreign language. Moreover, in this case we are also talking about the organization of students' independent work, which is a transitional link in the process of formation and development of students' creative potential. [2] The students themselves write a scenario, organize rehearsals, distribute roles, appoint persons responsible for the performance of this or that part of the work. Analyzing the available experience in conducting such events, we can state that students participate in such work with great pleasure, enthusiasm, emotional boost, their motivation increases significantly, and, achieving radically new results, respectively, we move to a whole new level of foreign language teaching at the university. As experience shows, such forms of work, combined with traditional grammar exercises, not only improve the results, but are also a powerful motivational tool for learning a foreign language. Moreover, in this case we are also talking about the organi-

zation of students' independent work, which is a transitional link in the process of formation and development of students' creative potential. [2] The students themselves write a scenario, organize rehearsals, distribute roles, appoint persons responsible for the performance of this or that part of the work. Analyzing the available experience in conducting such events, we can state that students participate in such work with great pleasure, enthusiasm, emotional boost, their motivation increases significantly, and, achieving radically new results, respectively, we move to a whole new level of foreign language teaching at the university.

As supplementary material, the use of texts of articles on the specialty in issue is extremely important. Our aim is to teach future professionals to use foreign language authentic sources of information in the context of their future profession. Although they are constantly working with texts from textbooks, it is advisable to organize and pay special attention to this type of material, as students often find it difficult to perceive and process information in an unusual format. In this case it is suggested to read the text of an article, to identify the main topics, to highlight the main points from each section – to formulate them in one or two phrases. A text map or a table helps with such tasks, when we structure all the information, which facilitates better learning. For example, on the topic "Jobs in the hospitality industry", the students use such a way of processing information as making a table:

Tab. 1. Jobs in Hospitality Industry.

Positions	Responsibilities	Hard skills	Soft skills
Hotel management: director of hotel sales, group sales manager, hotel manager, lodging manager, shift manager, guest room sales manager, shift leader, spa manager and shift manager.	Individuals in hotel management positions are responsible for ensuring hotel operations, run smoothly and that guests are satisfied with their experience during their stay. These professionals regularly interact with guests and employees, manage staff, oversee the budget of the hotel	Knowledge of standards Business skills Business acumen Management skills Financial management Operational knowledge Industry awareness Marketing skills Sales skills Risk management Budgeting Forecasting	Interpersonal skills Communication skills Team building Flexibility Leadership skills Detail orientation Initiative Adaptability Reliability Multitasking skills Time management Problem-solving skills

	and perform general management duties.	Guest services skills Real estate knowledge Customer service skills	Active listening skills Professionalism Work ethic
Front desk: concierge, front-of-house manager, front desk associate, hotel clerk, hotel receptionist, guest services associate, front office attendant, reservations agent, guest services supervisor and front desk supervisor.	Front desk employees are considered customer-facing workers and regularly interact with customers in their day-to-day duties. They provide customers with various services, assist in answering questions and concerns and anticipate customer needs to provide an excellent customer experience.	Knowledge of standards Organization skills Guest service Customer service skills Inventory management Knowledge of POS Payroll operations Sales skills Accountability Managerial skills Leadership skills Multitasking skills Cultural awareness	Listening skills Patience Setting a goal Interpersonal communication skills Enthusiasm Teamwork skills Conflict resolution Computer skills Problem solving skills Communication skills Flexibility Adaptability Initiative Emotional Intelligence Time management Stress Management
Kitchen personnel: catering manager, chef, executive chef, cook, kitchen manager, sous chef, pastry chef, food and beverage manager and restaurant manager.	Professionals who work in the kitchen are an integral part of the hospitality industry. They work in restaurants, hotels, venues, casinos and any other location that services food to customers.	Knowledge of standards Culinary expertise Heat control Presentation skills Administrative skills Business acumen Inventory management Foodservice management Customer service skills Sanitary practices Collaboration skills Food preparation skills Knife skills Catering skills	Physical stamina Teamwork skills Time management skills Attention to detail Motivation Conceptual thinking Creativity skills Good hygiene Decision-making skills Initiative Communication skills Organization skills Flexibility
Valet and concierge: baggage porter, valet, valet attendant, bell attendant, driver, bellhop, valet parking attendant and parking lot attendant.	Valet staff is responsible for handling customer baggage, valeting customers' vehicles and offering other support services to hospitality staff.	Knowledge of standards Guest luggage Valet service skills Car parking and retrieval Customer service skills Knowledge of various types of vehicles Manual and automatic transmission skills Driving skills	Professionalism Communication skills Physical stamina Attention to detail Good memory Flexibility
Waitstaff: server, som-	Waitresses and waiters	Knowledge of standards	Communication skills

<p>melier, head waiter, food server, food runner, bartender, barback, waiter, barista, hostess and catering assistant.</p>	<p>work in restaurants and other hospitality environments and directly interact with customers to take orders, serve beverages and food and take payments.</p>	<p>Detail orientation Customer service skills Basic math skills Conflict resolution POS systems</p>	<p>Interpersonal skills Memorization skills Stress management Time management Emotional intelligence Physical stamina Teamwork skills Professionalism High energy Persistence Active listening skills Attentiveness Dependability Service orientation Motivation Multitasking skills Critical thinking skills Dexterity</p>
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Moreover, texts used as a resource for the above-mentioned tasks can also stimulate students' independent, research or project activities. We can use a variety of materials that align in content with the topics being studied as well as complementary ones that broaden students' general horizons. For example, consider the article "Cruise line jobs"⁴. This article is offered as a part of the "Cruise Industry" topic studied in Tourism and Hospitality. We use a variety of tasks, for example, asking students to compare jobs on a cruise liner and in a hotel, incorporating these types of supplementary material into the teaching process.

As a rule, working with a particular group of students during a semester, it becomes clear what types of tasks may be preferable, what should be particularly focused on, etc. An extremely important part of the teacher's work is the timely recording of interim results and identifying further vector of movement in skills development. We clearly see what the students have already achieved, their successes and achievements, and according to this, build a further strategy and trajectory of movement. Throughout the process, it is important to take an individual approach and pay attention to each student, noting their progress, even if it seems insignificant at first glance. A comfortable psychological envi-

ronment and support is always a great incentive for continued success.

Due to the extremely fast changing external environment, we clearly see the need to respond in the foreign language classroom by using all modern forms, resources, possibilities. In addition, it is important to note that the inclusion of a variety of sources in the learning process provides students with the opportunity to get to know and master different stylistic solutions. Blogs, vlogs, reviews written by professional journalists, critics, tourists, customers, guests of restaurants, hotels, etc. can be used. By building foreign language learning in this format, students respond to short messages, write responses to complaints, master the formal and informal language of professional communication, which significantly helps them to prepare themselves directly for their chosen industry.

Clearly structured assignments also play a huge role in designing and planning lessons with students, saving time, which is the most valuable resource in modern life.

Assignments can be content-based, i.e. involving the provision of material, or they can be unrelated to the material or a specific topic. For example, in the first case we consider all assignments which include texts, articles, interviews, etc. containing specific content – "content-based" tasks. In the second case,

⁴ <https://www.soegjobs.com/apply-cruise-line-jobs/>

we consider tasks that are not tied to a particular topic, so-called "task-based" tasks, e.g. shoot a video clip, conduct an interview, write a review, without restricting students to choose the content they use at their own convenience. In this case, students focus on the task itself rather than on the language and content part. [9] Task-based learning is not a new phenomenon. Prabhu, a teacher from South India used it with secondary school students as early as 1979, after which it became widespread in foreign language teaching practices all over the world.[10]

All the tasks are very closely interwoven and interconnected. If not enough attention is paid

to just one link, the whole structure can collapse. This is why it is so important not to miss anything when planning and developing assignments, using a flexible approach and taking into account all necessary factors. Only a careful analysis, variability of use, clear adaptation of existing tasks to the audience we are working with, the level of language background of the students, the specifics of the course, obligatory consideration of the individual characteristics of each student, their level of motivation can together give the expected high results in foreign language teaching at university.

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